

Application of Blockchain Technologies in Various Areas

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Abstract: blockchain technology, although it has recently appeared, has already gained popularity due to its security and reliability, and is potentially of great importance for various transactions. Although its main application is economics, cryptocurrencies, the technology is potentially useful in various fields, and its many possibilities have not yet been put into practice. The article briefly discusses its principles of operation and possible applications in various sectors of the economy.

Keywords: blockchain, future technologies, information technology.

Blockchain (English blockchain, originally block chain - chain of blocks) is a continuous sequential chain of blocks (linked list) built according to certain rules, containing any information. The connection between blocks is ensured not only by numbering, but also by the presence in each block of its own hash sum and the hash sum of the previous block. Changing any information in a block changes its hash sum. To comply with the chaining rules, changes in the hash sum must be written to the next block, which leads to a change in its own hash sum. In this case, previous blocks are not affected. If the block being changed is the last block in the chain, then making changes may not require much effort. However, if the continuation has already been formed after the block is changed, then the change can be a very time-consuming process. The fact is that usually copies of block chains are stored independently of each other on different computers. This term first appeared as the name of a fully replicated distributed database implemented in the Bitcoin system, which is why the blockchain is often referred to as a book of transactions in various cryptocurrencies. However, blockchain technology can be extended to any number of interconnected blocks of information. The Bitcoin system, introduced in October 2008, was the first use of blockchain technology. Currently, blockchain technologies are used in areas such as financial transactions, user identification or the creation of cybersecurity technologies, and are also relevant for banking institutions and government organizations.

Blockchain technology is based on the concept of a distributed ledger of information that is stored and managed by multiple network participants in a decentralized manner. Blockchain provides transparency, security and reliability in maintaining records of transactions, transactions and other interactions. Initially developed to support cryptocurrencies, blockchain technologies have attracted worldwide attention in recent years. This technology allows the creation of decentralized and secure databases that can be used to store, share and verify information without the intervention of central authorities.

- Blockchain technology can be used in various industries, and some of them have already started using it to optimize their processes. Below are some of the industries where blockchain technology has found its application:

➤ Blockchain technology can be used in many industries. Some of them include:

1. Financial sector: Blockchain can be used to improve payment systems, transfer money, and exchange value. It can also be used in credit and insurance transactions, as well as in the issuance of financial instruments. Blockchain allows for the simplification and acceleration of processes in the financial sector. This can include reducing the time it takes to complete financial transactions, eliminating the need for intermediaries, increasing security, and reducing transaction costs. Cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin are based on blockchain and are already widely used in the financial sector.

2. Supply and logistics: Blockchain allows for the tracking of the route and status of shipments. This helps prevent counterfeiting and control the supply chain. Blockchain can be used to create supply chains that are more transparent and secure. It allows goods or products to be tracked from the time they are manufactured to the final consumer. This can improve control over the quality and safety of products, as well as reduce the risk of counterfeiting.

3. Healthcare: Blockchain can be used to securely and transparently store patient medical data, and share access between doctors and healthcare-related transactions. Blockchain can be used to create digital medical records that are securely stored and can only be accessed by authorized individuals. This allows for more efficient and secure sharing of medical information between different healthcare stakeholders, eliminating the possibility of data fraud.

4. Voting: Blockchain can provide security and privacy protection for electronic voting, eliminating the possibility of forgery and manipulation. Blockchain can create digital identities and other documents that can be verified in real time and without the need to visit central institutions. This can significantly simplify and speed up the processes of interaction with government services.

5. Intellectual property and copyright: Blockchain allows for the creation and management of digital assets, including music, films and art, and protects the rights and interests of copyright holders. Blockchain can support secure communication between Internet of Things devices and ensure the secure storage and transmission of data. This will contribute to the wider development and use of the Internet of Things.

As a technology for creating public distributed databases, blockchain faces a number of unique challenges that make it difficult to use. These problems include:

- the constant growth of the size of blockchain files
- limitations in the capacity of communication channels between network nodes and the difficulty of synchronizing individual replicas associated with this limitation
- a general limitation on blockchain performance associated with the specific operation of consensus algorithms

The development of new types of blockchains often involves overcoming or circumventing these problems and limitations. At the same time, there are a number of functions that a blockchain system cannot perform without:

Data is stored in a block chain structure, in which each block is linked to the previous one. Changing the data in a block is impossible without changing all subsequent blocks.

- Each network participant has a copy of all data (the entire blockchain). Participants communicate with each other in a peer-to-peer format.
- A consensus mechanism is established - a certain interaction of nodes that ensures the correctness of the data recorded in the next block of the chain and the achievement of an agreement on the choice of a block included in the chain from several possible

alternatives.

These are just a few examples of areas where blockchain technology can be used. The potential of blockchain is enormous, and it continues to find new applications in various fields and activities. For example, in the banking sector, investments and exchanges, land registry, identity cards, means of payment, the gaming industry, online voting, the construction business, etc. These are just some of the areas where blockchain technology has already shown its potential. As the technology advances and the commercial applications of blockchain expand, the number of applications is expected to continue to grow.

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